

DEVELOPMENT OF A CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK JOINT DETECTOR FOR NON-ORTHOGONAL MULTIPLE ACCESS UPLINK RECEIVERS

Raed S. H. AL-Musawi

*Department of Electrical Engineering
University of Babylon
Najaf str., Babylon, Iraq, 51001*

Ali Hilal Ali ✉

*Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering
University of Kufa
Kufa str., Najaf, Iraq, 54001
alih.alathari@uokufa.edu.iq*

Kadhun Al-Majdi

*Department of Medical Techniques
Ashur University College
Hay Alwaziriya str., Baghdad, Iraq, 995P+J9P*

Sarmad Al Gayar

*Department of Automatic and Computers
Politehnica University of Bucharest
313 Splaiul Independenței str., Bucharest, Romania, 060042*

✉ Corresponding author

Abstract

We present a novel approach to signal detection for Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) uplink receivers using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in a single-shot fashion. The defacto NOMA detection method is the so-called Successive Interference Cancellation which requires precise channel estimation and accurate successive detection of the user equipment with the higher powers. It is proposed converting incoming packets into 2D image-like streams. These images are fed to a CNN-based deep learning network commonly used in the image processing literature for image classification. The classification label for each packet converted to an image is the transmitted symbols by all user equipment joined together. CNN network is trained using uniformly distributed samples of incoming packets at different signals to noise ratios. Furthermore, let's performed hyperparameter optimization using the exhaustive search method. Our approach is tested using a modeled system of two user equipment systems in a 64-subcarrier Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) and Rayleigh channel. It is found that a three-layer CNN with 32 filters of size 7×7 has registered the highest training and testing accuracy of about 81. In addition, our result showed significant improvement in Symbol Error Rate (SER) vs. Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) compared to other state-of-the-art approaches such as least square, minimum mean square error, and maximum likelihood under various channel conditions. When the channel length is fixed at 20, our approach is at least one significant Figure better than the maximum likelihood method at (SNR) of 2 dB. Finally, the channel length to 12 is varied and it is registered about the same performance. Hence, our approach is more robust to joint detection in NOMA receivers, particularly in low signal-to-noise environments.

Keywords: deep learning, non-orthogonal multiple access, convolutional neural network, hyperparameter tuning.

DOI: 10.21303/2461-4262.2022.002496

1. Introduction

The requirements for next-generation wireless telecommunications call for the support of an ever-growing user base, a significant amount of multimedia traffic, and large-scale internet-of-things (IoT) [1]. Although current multiple access techniques such as Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) have enabled resource sharing among users and devices for a long time, they are inefficient, in terms of spectral-usage, enough to satisfy the vast traffic varieties needed by 5G networks [2].

One promising solution for the problem of spectral usage is the so-called Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) techniques. It has generated a tremendous amount of interest and attracted researchers due to its spectral efficiency [3], lower latency [4], diverse power management policies [5], and support for a larger amount of users [6].

In traditional multiple access systems based on the OFDM paradigm, information from users is assigned to some dedicated subcarriers, and guard intervals are inserted to reduce the effect of interference. Hence, the inefficient use of spectrum [2].

In NOMA, users can access all subcarriers, and their information is superimposed in a non-orthogonal fashion at the transmitter [7]. The complexity of NOMA requires algorithms with high computational power to successfully decode information of all users. Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) is the de-facto method for that end. It starts by detecting the user's signal with the highest power while treating everyone else signals as noise. Once this is done, that signal is subtracted from the original stream, the next user signal is detected, and so on [8]. NOMA ensures fairness to all users by assigning more power to those users with worse channel conditions [9]. For that to work, perfect Channel State Information needs to be maintained for the superiority of NOMA over traditional OFDMA to stand [2].

Traditional methods based on SIC requires accurate channel estimation [10]. Channel estimation error would result in loss of link robustness and reliability [11]. In addition, SIC requires users sorted out in terms of signal power in ordered to be detected sequentially. If the user with the highest power is not detected correctly, then all is lost [12]. Hence, it is decided to seek a scheme where link performance, reliability and robustness would not be affected by loss of channel estimation and/or the sequential nature of the SIC receiver.

Lately, there has been tremendous research on the use of Deep Learning (DL) in communication systems. In particular, for the detection of users' signals in NOMA. Deep Learning is a subset of machine learning used to design models that can learn from data examples. It has attracted huge interest due to its capability of learning complex models with high accuracy [13]. For instance, DL multitasking has been used to learn channel estimation, mapping, and detecting users' signals [14]. Multitasking is a powerful DL concept where DL can be trained to perform many functions simultaneously. However, their work was not purely an end-to-end data-driven approach as it required some domain knowledge. What makes DL multitasking so powerful is parameter sharing [15], but there was no evidence of using such powerful and efficient techniques. Similarly, DL has been used for detecting the modulation mode in NOMA [16], joint multi-user detection [10], and analysis of CSI and transmitted sequence detection [8]. Let's suggest reference [17] for a more detailed survey.

However, the effective use of DL lies in its ability to work in an end-to-end fashion where little-to-no preprocessing, feature engineering modularization is required. Let's propose enhancing the single-shot multi-user detection scheme in [18]. A single (Long Short-Term Memory) LSTM DL network is used as an end-to-end system for channel estimation and decoding users' signals in an uplink scenario. A similar work has been proposed in [19].

A major issue with these approaches is overfitting, also known as high variance. Overfitting is a measure of the generalization capabilities of a DL network. It can be implied when there is a significant gap/difference between training and testing accuracies. Replication of the LSTM network training proposed in [18] has resulted in a significant overfitting. In addition, LSTM requires unrolling of incoming users' packets which would result in longer-term dependencies. Longer-term dependencies often give rise to vanishing gradient problems.

A better generation approach for the training data and hyperparameter optimization can dramatically reduce the effect of high variance. The contribution of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- propose a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based detector rather than a LSTM as in the literature. LSTM requires unrolling of incoming packets into a single stream. Such unrolling would result in longer term dependencies between LSTM units and in turn gives rise to exploding/vanishing gradients during training [20];

- to the best of our knowledge, forming images from incoming packets in the context of NOMA receivers has not been proposed before in the literature successfully. Let's show how using CNN rather than LSTM can improve the DL-based NOMA receiver's performance and robustness;

- perform model selection by hyperparameter optimization using exhaustive search. Some hyperparameters include the number of layers, number of filters, and the size of filter. Such a step is often neglected in the literature;
- improve the generalization capability of the CNN network by reducing overfitting. Other efforts in the literature often result in overfitting which are rarely discussed;
- discuss how to better prepare the training dataset to avoid high variance/overfitting.

2. Materials and methods

This section will elaborate on the methods used to create the training dataset artificially, the deep learning models, evaluate the results, and fine-tune the performance. Let's propose an end-to-end deep learning model where the input is the received packets from user equipment 1 and 2 and the output is a label representing the detected symbols transmitted by the two users. Hence, there would be no pre-processing, feature extraction, and/or stages of deep learning models trained to model channels, perform equalization and detect symbols separately. Everything is done in a single-shot-like manner.

This paper utilizes deep learning as an end-to-end NOMA receiver in an uplink scenario. To satisfy the end-to-end objective, the deep learning model should detect users' signals in a one-shot fashion by implicitly performing channel estimation and decoding. Thus, let's decide to improve upon reference [18], where only the initial results were reported. Let's show how a change of DL architecture from LSTM to CNN, a better generation scheme of training data, and hyperparameter tuning can significantly increase accuracy and robustness.

To keep the comparison fair, let's also consider the case of two User Equipment (UE) connected to a base station, each with a single antenna in an uplink scenario, as depicted in **Fig. 1**. Each UE transmits OFDM with a 64-subcarriers data packet. Hence, the base station will receive an overlay of packets from UE 1 and 2, pilot packets, and added noise. Let's elaborate on the constituents of the received packets in the next section. Additionally, let's assume perfect CSI knowledge at both the transmitter and receiver.

Fig. 1. Basic Scenario of two user equipment in a NOMA Uplink

The received signal at subcarrier (t) under the assumption of (K) users and (M) subcarriers can be written as [18]:

$$Y(t) = \sum_{i=1}^K \sqrt{P_i(t)} H_i(t) X_i(t) + \Psi(t), \quad (1)$$

where $Y(t)$ is the amount of received signal, $P_i(t)$ is the power transmitted by user (i) at subcarrier (t), $\Psi(t)$ is the amount of noise modelled as additive white gaussian noise, and $H_i(t)$ is the multipath channel $h_i(t)$ given by its discrete Fourier transform. It can be expressed as [18]:

$$h_i(t) = \sum_{\lambda=1}^{\xi} \theta_{i,\lambda} \rho(t - \tau_{i,\xi}), \quad (2)$$

where $\theta_{i,\lambda}$ the complex channel gain and $\tau_{i,\xi}$ is its subsequent delay for user (i) down path (λ). In order for us to fairly compare our approach to the previously published work, let's assume

a Rayleigh fading channel with total delay (ζ) of 20, a total signal power (P) of unity and a power allocation coefficient for user (i) of $\sigma_i(t) = P_i(t)/P$ [18].

3. Results and discussion

Referring to **Fig. 2, a**, let's use MATLAB software to implement a 64-subcarrier OFDM system by generating an artificial dataset of random Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK) symbols representing signals from user equipment 1 and 2. Additionally, two fixed pilot sequences are generated, making each OFDM packet consist of 3 symbols. Two symbols for the pilot sequence, and the third is a data symbol from the two users. A cyclic prefix (CP) is inserted to the time-domain equivalent of the OFDM symbol, i.e., after taking the inverse DFT. Finally, the noise was added to the received packet described early. **Fig. 2, b** shows a typical OFDM packet where the subscript (d) stands for: data packet and the subscript (p) refers to a pilot packet.

Fig. 2. Data acquisition, processing and training procedure:
a – modelling workflow by deep learning; *b* – the formation of the received OFDM packet into an image of size 64×4

The training dataset is formed by treating the received packet as an image. This image comprises the real and imaginary parts of the received packets. Since there are three packets of 64 sub-carriers, there will be 64×3×2 data points. It is reshaped that vector into a 64×6 image, **Fig. 2, b**. Then, each image is paired with its corresponding output label. Since the two users are modulated with QPSK, which has four symbols, there will be 16 different combinations of the label that could be transmitted by them jointly [18].

Next, let's use various levels of E_g/N_o ranging from 5 to 40 dB during the generation of the dataset. Our reasoning was to avoid overfitting and improve accuracy. Since a good training dataset should have examples of all typical cases and extreme cases that expect the model to encounter in real-life scenarios. If to train the model using only partial cases of high E_g/N_o levels, then bias towards high E_g/N_o values may occur. On the other hand, if the level of E_g/N_o chosen for training were low, then overfitting may occur as the model fails to generalize from cases that are essentially overwhelmed with random noise.

For the CNN model, let's use MATLAB deep learning toolbox to construct two convolutional layers. Each layer will have a tuneable number of filters, and filter size commonly referred to as hyperparameters. It is possible to fine-tune the model's performance to increase its classification accuracy by changing these hyperparameters. Let's use the ReLU activation function following each convolution layer. Any pooling layer did not use due to the small size of the image. CNN's are essentially a feature extraction filter. It makes deep learning work without manually coming up with a feature extraction plan. Hence, a fully connected network is needed to classify the extracted features. The Softmax layer normalizes the output of the fully connected layer to the probability density function over the 16 output labels. Finally, the classification layer outputs the most probable label.

Fig. 3 shows the CNN model was obtained after the hyperparameter tuning step. The CNN architecture consists of three convolutional layers. Each convolutional layer uses 64 filters of size (7,7). Since the input image size is small, let's pad the image before applying the convolution step. However, let's used a step size, also called stride, of 2 to avoid overlapping while convolving the image. This seems to have given us a better result. A cross-correlation equation used for implementing the convolution operation is described in reference [13]:

$$\Gamma(i, j) = (I * K)(i, j) = \sum_M \sum_N I(i + M, j + N) K(M, N), \quad (3)$$

where Γ is the convolution function between the image and I filter K and (M, N) is the dimensions of the image I , usually, this operation is followed by a nonlinear function such as sigmoid, tanh, or ReLU, let's use ReLU due to its fast convergence rate.

Fig. 3. CNN Architecture obtained after hyperparameter tuning

The purpose of the CNN layers is to act as an automatic feature extractor. It is automatic in the sense that the transformation from images to features is learned from the data. Once this is done, a fully connected layer with 16 neurons is used to separate the classes from each other, shown in **Fig. 3** as fc1. The softmax layer calculates the probability of each image belonging to a class. Finally, the classification layer picks the class with the highest probability as the detected symbol. Let's use MATLAB Deep Learning Toolbox to carry out the modeling and optimization procedure throughout this work. Artificial data was generated at six E_g/N_o values ranging from 5 to 40 dB with a step of 7 dB. For each level, 1000 samples per label was generated. This would give a total of 96000 samples arranged as images of size (64.6). Let's divide the dataset into training and testing sets with a ratio of 90 % for training and 10 % for testing. These figures are only 1/5th the number of samples needed by recent research work [18].

Let's use this dataset to optimize the performance of our model. The procedure is straightforward. Let's gradually change one hyperparameter while keeping all others fixed and noted its effect on the training accuracy. Then, let's change another hyperparameter and so on. **Table 1** summarizes the results of that procedure.

At a single CNN layer, let's notice that the performance was poor, and increasing the number of filters did not improve performance significantly. Hence, let's add a second CNN layer and then a third layer. Furthermore, increasing stride and filter size dramatically impacted performance, reaching its maximum in run number 11, where the training and validation accuracy was slightly above 81 % accuracy. This may be because increasing stride size will compensate for the padding added in each layer to maintain image size and that more features are required to

class this. Finally, the training and testing accuracy gap is significantly tiny, indicating excellent generalization capabilities.

Table 1

Results of the hyperparameter tuning procedure

Run No.	No. of CNN layers	No. of filters	Filter size	Stride size	Training accuracy (%)	Testing accuracy (%)
1	1	4	(3,3)	1	6.92	5.92
2	1	8	(3,3)	1	7.00	6.11
3	2	4	(3,3)	1	6.00	6.08
4	2	4	(5,5)	1	6.17	5.96
5	2	8	(3,3)	1	6.40	6.01
6	3	8	(3,3)	1	6.08	6.11
7	3	16	(3,3)	1	6.34	6.04
8	3	16	(5,5)	1	6.05	6.21
9	3	16	(5,5)	2	39.24	38.09
10	3	16	(7,7)	2	48.30	47.81
11	3	32	(7,7)	2	61.11	60.10
12	3	64	(7,7)	2	81.98	81.74

Next, let's show the Symbol Error Rate (SER) curves using our model obtained after hyperparameter tuning versus other conventional methods. The ones we are considering are Maximum Likelihood and SIC. A standard procedure is followed where the channel is estimated using Least Squares (LS) and Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) as described in [18, 21]. A 100,000 data packet is used during simulation to measure the SER vs. SNR of our proposed DL model vs. the previously mentioned methods. Let's assume a fixed phase shift with a maximum CP length of 20 and perfect channel state information.

Fig. 4 shows the SER vs. SNR curves for UE1 and UE2 using our proposed CNN-based DL network versus LS, MMSE, and ML. Our approach is shown red named DL for Deep Learning. For UE1, our method has far exceeded the performance of the traditional techniques and showed almost linear behavior, especially in low SNR values. It proves that a better training data generation scheme that includes data samples at both low and high SNR values and an effective tuning procedure can result in a powerful NOMA receiver.

Fig. 5 shows the robustness of the proposed DL network when the CP is changed from 20 to 12. Since this value is shorter than the channel length, LS and MMSE cannot keep perfect channel information, unlike our DL network, which outperformed both methods laying slightly behind the ML, which represents the theoretical limit. At a CP value of 20, our DL network still outperforms all other methods by a significant margin.

The impact of these results can be summarized in two folds. Firstly, let's eliminate the need for SIC. Consequently, the requirements for accurate channel estimation which is important in order to keep reliable link performance. In addition, the sequential nature of the SIC detector where the user with the strongest power is detected first and then the others is replaced by a one-shot detection scheme. Secondly, let's exceed the performance the theoretical maximum likelihood receiver by one significant figure by hyper parameter optimization and training the DL network at uniformly sampled data at various SNR values rather than at the highest SNR level as the case in the literature. This has reduced overfitting and improved generalization capabilities.

These results suggest CNN-based deep learning model as a strong candidate for the next generation wireless communication channel. However, our modelling and simulation were limited to two users only which is the defacto testing paradigm in the literature. Increasing the number of user is helpful in assessing the scalability of deep learning. In addition, an accuracy of about 82 % is obtained. While this is higher than the state-of-the-art methods, a higher rate is desirable to avoid model bias.

Fig. 4. SER vs SNR of the proposed CNN network against LS, MMSE and ML:
a – SER vs SNR for UE 1 where the CNN DL method is shown in red and labelled as (DL); *b* – SER vs SNR for UE 2 where the CNN DL method is shown in red and labelled as (DL)

Fig. 5. SER vs SNR for various lengths of CPs for the proposed CNN network vs LS, MMSE and ML methods: *a* – SER vs SNR for UE1 shown in red; *b* – SER vs SNR for UE2 shown in red

In summary, the superior spectral usage efficiency and support for a massive number of users and services have made NOMA a promising technology for the next generation wireless communication system. However, detection and channel estimation within non-orthogonal multiple access is a challenging problem where several solutions have been proposed.

SIC is the default method for detecting NOMA packets. However, its need for perfect channel state estimation to maintain reliable and robust link performance and the sequential nature of the detection procedure, has led research to search for alternatives.

One alternative is Deep Learning LSTM networks which we showed some examples in the literature. The main issue with this approach is the unfolding of received packets which may lead to vanishing gradients in addition to poor training procedures which resulted in overfitting.

4. Conclusions

We have presented a convolutional neural network (CNN) based DL network where incoming packets are turned into 2-D images and fed into a three-layer CNN for classification in a one-shot fashion. CNN acts as a feature extractor through a tunable filter learned from examples.

Our approach was proved using a two-user equipment scenario where a 64-subcarrier OFDM system is used. Data packets were transmitted using a simulated Rayleigh channel. The CNN-based DL performs both channel estimation and decoding for both user equipment implicitly. The training and testing accuracies were about 80. Similar figures mean no overfitting. The resulting network is compared to other state-of-the-art approaches including maximum likelihood and successive interference cancellation. Our approach has shown superior performance and robustness against conventional methods under various channel conditions by a significant margin at a low SNR of 2 dB and steady robustness when the channel length is varied from 20 to 12.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Kufa, Babylon and Ashur Universities for providing equipment and computation power throughout this project. We also thank Dr Sarmad for the financial support and dedication.

References

- [1] Chin, W., Fan, Z., Haines, R. (2014). Emerging technologies and research challenges for 5G wireless networks. *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 21 (2), 106–112. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/mwc.2014.6812298>
- [2] Hasan, M. K., Shahjalal, M., Islam, M. M., Alam, M. M., Ahmed, M. F., Jang, Y. M. (2020). The Role of Deep Learning in NOMA for 5G and Beyond Communications. 2020 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Information and Communication (ICAIIIC). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/icaaic48513.2020.9065219>
- [3] Khan, W. U., Liu, J., Jameel, F., Sharma, V., Jantti, R., Han, Z. (2020). Spectral Efficiency Optimization for Next Generation NOMA-Enabled IoT Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 69 (12), 15284–15297. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tvt.2020.3038387>
- [4] Ye, Y., Hu, R. Q., Lu, G., Shi, L. (2020). Enhance Latency-Constrained Computation in MEC Networks Using Uplink NOMA. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 68 (4), 2409–2425. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tcomm.2020.2969666>
- [5] Park, S., Truong, A. Q., Nguyen, T. H. (2019). Power Control for Sum Spectral Efficiency Optimization in MIMO-NOMA Systems With Linear Beamforming. *IEEE Access*, 7, 10593–10605. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2018.2890441>
- [6] Shin, W., Vaezi, M., Lee, J., Poor, H. V. (2016). On the number of users served in MIMO-NOMA cellular networks. 2016 International Symposium on Wireless Communication Systems (ISWCS). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/iswcs.2016.7600982>
- [7] Kizilirmak, R. C. (2016). Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) for 5G Networks. *Towards 5G Wireless Networks – A Physical Layer Perspective*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5772/66048>
- [8] Chen, X., Jia, R., Ng, D. W. K. (2019). On the Design of Massive Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access With Imperfect Successive Interference Cancellation. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 67 (3), 2539–2551. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tcomm.2018.2884476>
- [9] Yang, Z., Ding, Z., Fan, P., Karagiannidis, G. K. (2016). On the Performance of Non-orthogonal Multiple Access Systems With Partial Channel Information. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 64 (2), 654–667. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tcomm.2015.2511078>
- [10] Emir, A., Kara, F., Kaya, H., Yanikomeroglu, H. (2021). DeepMuD: Multi-User Detection for Uplink Grant-Free NOMA IoT Networks via Deep Learning. *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, 10 (5), 1133–1137. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/lwc.2021.3060772>
- [11] Guo, S., Zhou, X. (2019). Robust Resource Allocation With Imperfect Channel Estimation in NOMA-Based Heterogeneous Vehicular Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 67 (3), 2321–2332. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tcomm.2018.2885999>
- [12] Ghazi, H. S., Wesolowski, K. W. (2019). Improved Detection in Successive Interference Cancellation NOMA OFDM Receiver. *IEEE Access*, 7, 103325–103335. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2019.2931809>
- [13] Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y., Courville, A. (2016). *Deep Learning*. MIT Press, 800.
- [14] Ye, N., Li, X., Yu, H., Zhao, L., Liu, W., Hou, X. (2020). DeepNOMA: A Unified Framework for NOMA Using Deep Multi-Task Learning. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 19 (4), 2208–2225. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/twc.2019.2963185>
- [15] Ruder, S. (2017). An overview of multi-task learning in deep neural networks. *arXiv*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1706.05098>
- [16] Xie, W., Xiao, J., Yang, J., Peng, X., Yu, C., Zhu, P. (2020). Deep learning-based modulation detection for NOMA systems. *arXiv*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2005.11684>
- [17] Andiappan, V., Ponnusamy, V. (2021). Deep Learning Enhanced NOMA System: A Survey on Future Scope and Challenges. *Wireless Personal Communications*, 123 (1), 839–877. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-021-09160-1>

- [18] Narengerile, Thompson, J. (2019). Deep Learning for Signal Detection in Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access Wireless Systems. 2019 UK/ China Emerging Technologies (UCET). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ucet.2019.8881888>
- [19] Emir, A., Kara, F., Kaya, H., Yanikomeroglu, H. (2021). Deep Learning Empowered Semi-Blind Joint Detection in Cooperative NOMA. IEEE Access, 9, 61832–61852. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2021.3074350>
- [20] Zhang, J., Lin, Y., Song, Z., Dhillon, I. (2018). Learning long term dependencies via fourier recurrent units. Proceedings of the 35th International Conference on Machine Learning. Available at: <http://proceedings.mlr.press/v80/zhang18h/zhang18h.pdf>
- [21] Edfors, O., Sandell, M., van de Beek, J.-J., Wilson, S. K., Borjesson, P. O. (1998). OFDM channel estimation by singular value decomposition. IEEE Transactions on Communications, 46 (7), 931–939. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/26.701321>

Received date 19.04.2022

Accepted date 04.07.2022

Published date 30.07.2022

© The Author(s) 2022

This is an open access article
under the Creative Commons CC BY license

How to cite: AL-Musawi, R. S. H., Ali, A. H., Al-Majdi, K., Al Gayar, S. (2022). Development of a convolutional neural network joint detector for non-orthogonal multiple access uplink receivers. *EUREKA: Physics and Engineering*, 4, 179–178. <https://doi.org/10.21303/2461-4262.2022.002496>